

Metal Complexes of Thiopolycarboxylic Acid (III) : Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) Complexes with Methylenedithioacetic Acid and Their Pyridine Derivatives

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Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) with methylenedithioacetic acid and their pyridine derivatives were prepared. Structures have been characterised on the basis of magnetic moment, electronic and infrared spectral studies. The results are in agreement with the octahedral arrangement of the coordination sphere of the metal ions studied.

IN continuation of our work on metal complexes of thiopolycarboxylic acids^{1,2}, the present paper extends our studies to the preparation and characterisation of methylenedithioacetic acid (MBTAA-H₂), CH₂(SCH₂COOH)₂ complexes with Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) and their pyridine derivatives. MBTAA-H₂ containing two thio and two carboxylic groups and nitrogen from pyridine as potential donors, may, therefore, combine in various polydentate modes.

Experimental

Chemicals : MBTAA-H₂ of 99.5% purity (Evans Chemetics, New York) was used without further purification. All other chemicals used were of chemically pure grade.

Preparation of the metal Complexes : MBTAA-H₂ form solid complexes with Co, Ni and Cu ions. These compounds were prepared by the general method described below using the metal chlorides for Co(II) and Ni(II) and nitrate for Cu(II), with reference to the Co(II)-MBTAA-H₂ complex.

25 ml aqueous solution of cobalt chloride was added to an equimolar solution of MBTAA-H₂ (75 ml) in alcohol. A few drops of concentrated solution of NaOH were then added and the resulting mixture were refluxed for seven hours. A violet coloured solid was then separated out on cooling in ice cold water. It was filtered and washed with water, alcohol and ether and dried in vacuum over CaCl₂.

Complexes of Ni(II) and Cu(II), in green and greenish yellow colour respectively were prepared by the similar method.

Pyridine Derivatives : Pyridine-MBTAA-H₂ complexes of Co(II) in dark violet, Ni(II) in dark green and Cu(II) in dark bluish green colour were

prepared by the similar method as described above, for Co(II)-MBTAA-H₂, after mixing MBTAA-H₂ and pyridine, in appropriate quantity, before adding metal and NaOH solutions.

All these complexes were slightly soluble in hot water and common organic solvents.

Physical Measurements : The instruments and methods have been given previously¹.

Results and Discussion

Results are given in Table 1. The decomposition temperatures which range between 160° and 298° indicate that the complexes are thermally quite stable. The molar conductance of these complexes in DMSO indicates the non-electrolytic nature of these complexes (Table 2).

Co(II) Complexes : The observed magnetic moments of 4.97 and 5.22 B.M. (Table 2) for Co(MBTAA) and Co(MBTAA).2Py respectively are in agreement with the generally accepted values 4.80-5.60 B.M. for high-spin octahedral Co(II) complexes³, suggests that these complexes are octahedral. The electronic spectra (Table 3) of Co(MBTAA) complex is consistent with the octahedral or tetragonal arrangement of the ligand. Since the complex formed has D_{4h} symmetry, the electronic spectra can, therefore, be interpreted in terms of metal ion surrounded by a weak ligand field of octahedral microsymmetry. The octahedral Co(II) complexes, generally, exhibit three spin-allowed bands corresponding to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(v_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(v_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(v_3)$ in order of increasing energies in the absorption spectra. However, the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(v_2)$ may or may not be observed because of the weakness and proximity to a strong (v_3) transition. The observed electronic spectra (Table 3) consists of two main bands. The

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF MBTAA-H₂ AND THEIR PYRIDINE COMPLEXES

Compound	%Metal		%Carbon		%Hydrogen		%Sulphur		%Nitrogen		Decomposition Temperature °C
	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	
Co(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄)	23.28	23.34	23.72	23.76	2.39	2.35	25.33	25.38	—	—	270
Ni(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄)	23.21	23.30	23.74	23.71	2.39	2.32	25.23	25.16	—	—	265
Cu(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄).2H ₂ O	21.62	21.64	20.44	20.38	3.43	3.34	21.82	21.75	—	—	160
Co(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄).2Py	13.53	13.48	46.89	46.82	3.70	3.76	14.72	14.78	6.43	6.39	298
Ni(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄).2Py	13.49	13.39	46.92	46.88	3.70	3.78	14.73	14.80	6.44	6.38	280
Cu(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄).2Py	14.37	14.45	46.40	46.48	3.66	3.72	14.57	14.68	6.36	6.28	200

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC MOMENT AND CONDUCTANCE MEASUREMENTS OF MBTAA-H₂ AND THEIR PYRIDINE COMPLEXES

Compound	Temp. (°K)	χ _M × 10 ⁶ uncorr. (c.g.s.)	χ _M × 10 ⁶ corr. (c.g.s.)	μ _{eff} B.M.	Molar conductance ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹
Co(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄)	298.0	10185.78	10276.80	4.97	2.1
Ni(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄)	298.0	4906.24	4297.26	3.21	2.2
Cu(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄).2H ₂ O	298.0	1413.16	1530.18	1.95	2.1
Co(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄).2Py	298.0	11122.12	11325.58	5.23	6.8
Ni(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄).2Py	298.0	4558.42	4761.88	3.88	7.3
Cu(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄).2Py	298.0	1214.86	1418.32	1.85	6.0

TABLE 3—DIFFUSE REFLECTANCE SPECTRA AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF MBTAA-H₂ AND THEIR PYRIDINE COMPLEXES

Compounds	Bands kK	Assignments	D _q cm ⁻¹	Racah's Parameter (B) cm ⁻¹	L.F.S.E. K cal/mole	ν ₂ /ν ₁	B*	E _p term (992/1041) B _{Ni²⁺} cm ⁻¹	
Co(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄)	7.80(ν ₁)	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{2g} (F) → ⁴ A _{2g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)	848	858	19.33	2.05	0.883	12872	859
	16.00(ν ₂)								
	19.60(ν ₃)								
Ni(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄)	8.40(ν ₁)	³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (P)	840	920	28.72	1.66	0.884	13800	—
	14.00(ν ₂)								
	25.00(ν ₃)								
Cu(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄).2H ₂ O	13.00	² E _g → ² T _{2g} (F) ⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)	1300	—	22.23	—	—	—	—
	8.00(ν ₁)								
Co(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄).2Py	8.00(ν ₁)	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{2g} (F) → ⁴ A _{2g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)	870	873	19.83	2.07	0.900	13090	871
	16.00(ν ₂)								
	20.00(ν ₃)								
Ni(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄).2Py	8.60(ν ₁)	³ A ₂ (F) → ³ T _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (P)	860	933	29.41	1.67	0.896	14000	—
	14.40(ν ₂)								
	25.40(ν ₃)								
Cu(C ₅ H ₆ S ₂ O ₄).2Py	14.00	² E _g → ² T _{2g}	1400	—	23.94	—	—	—	—

lowest energy band at 7.80 kK is, therefore, assigned as (ν₁) and the strong band at 19.60 kK as (ν₃). A third weak band observed at 16.00 kK is, however, assumed as (ν₂) transition. These observed bands are quite similar⁴ to [Co(H₂O)₆]²⁺. To resolve the position of (ν₂) transition, on the basis of octahedral symmetry, the ligand field parameters were calculated (Table 3) by the use of semi-empirical equations⁵. The calculated value of (ν₂), 16.28 kK using the relation⁶ ν₂ = ν₁ + 10 D_q, is in good agreement with the observed band at 16.00 kK. Further, Lever⁷ has shown that in case of an octahedral Co(II) complex the (ν₂) transition must have an energy approximately twice but not greater than 2.2 times that of (ν₁) transition. The

observed ratio (ν₂/ν₁) as 2.05 also supports the assignment of the band at 16.00 kK to (ν₂) corresponding to the transition ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}.

In case of Co(MBTAA).2Py complex the observed electronic spectra consists of three main bands at 8.00 kK (ν₁); 16.60 kK (ν₂) and 20.00 kK (ν₃). These bands also correspond to other octahedral Co(II) complexes. The calculated value of ν₂ at 16.70 kK and observed ratio ν₂/ν₁ as 2.07 supports the octahedral structure of the complex. As discussed above the ligand field parameters (Table 3) were calculated on the basis of octahedral symmetry.

Ni(II) Complex : Our observed magnetic moment values of 3.21 and 3.38 B.M. for Ni(MBTAA) and Ni(MBTAA).2Py respectively (Table 2) clearly indicate the octahedral⁸ nature of these complexes.

The electronic spectra of the Ni(MBTAA) complex (Table 3) indicates a octahedral or tetragonal arrangement of the ligand. Although the complex formally has D_{4h} symmetry, the electronic spectrum in the range of 8.00-30.00 kK and magnetic moment value are typically of octahedrally coordinated Ni(II). The observed energies of the spin-allowed transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(\nu_1)$ at 8.40 kK, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)(\nu_2)$ at 14.00 kK and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$ at 25.00 kK agree well with those predicted from Liehr and Ballhausen⁹ energy level diagram for Ni(II) in a ligand field of octahedral symmetry. These bands are also very similar to those of nickel aquate¹⁰ $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$. The ligand field parameter, $10 Dq$ was taken equal to the observed energy of the first triplet transition (ν_1) and the Racah parameter, B was calculated by the substitution of (ν_1), (ν_2) and (ν_3) band energies in the secular equation¹¹. The calculation includes the mutual interaction between the T_{1g} levels but ignores spin-orbit coupling. The observed separation, 11.00 kK of (ν_2) and (ν_3) bands compared with the calculated value¹¹ of 11.04, on the basis of octahedral symmetry, further supports that the tetragonal distortion is rather small and the complex remains practically octahedral. Furthermore, our value of 1.66 for ratio (ν_2/ν_1) is in accord with the commonly reported value of 1.60-1.70 for Ni(II) complex of octahedral symmetry and indicates a strong T_{1g} levels interaction¹².

The observed electronic spectra of Ni(MBTAA).2Py complex also consists of three bands (Table 3) at 8.60 kK (ν_1), 14.40 kK (ν_2) and 25.40 kK (ν_3) as compared with Ni(MBTAA) complex. The observed separation, 11.00 kK of (ν_2) and (ν_3) band with the calculated value of 11.19 kK and the value of 1.67 for ratio (ν_2/ν_1) support that the Ni(MBTAA).2Py complex is also octahedral.

In these complexes the reduction of B after multiplying by $B \left(\frac{\text{Co}^{2+}}{\text{Ni}^{2+}} \right)$ gaseous, the so-called nephelauxetic effect¹³, seems to be more effective for Co(II) ion than for Ni(II) ion.

Cu(II) Complexes : Majority of Cu(II) complexes show magnetic moment values¹⁴ of 1.75-2.20 B.M. near the spin only value of 1.73 B.M. indicating the absence of any appreciable spin coupling between unpaired electrons belonging to different copper atoms. The magnetic moment of tetrahedral complexes are generally higher than the square planar or octahedral Cu(II) complexes^{3,15}. On the other hand, some complexes like Cu(II) carboxylates^{16,17} and the so-called tri-coordinated

Cu(II) complexes¹⁸ show a subnormal magnetic moment < 1.73 B.M. but not in all carboxyl group bridged polymers like Cu(II) benzoate trihydrate¹⁹ which has a magnetic moment of 1.87 B.M. The observed magnetic moment values of 1.95 and 1.85 B.M. for Cu(MBTAA) and Cu(MBTAA).2Py respectively (Table 2) excludes strong spin-spin pairing but does not exclude a polymeric structure.

The electronic spectra of an octahedrally coordinated Cu(II) complex should normally exhibit one absorption band due to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition. State 2E_g is highly susceptible to John Teller distortion and no Cu(II) complex should have a regular octahedral symmetry. The observed spectrum of Cu(MBTAA) and Cu(MBTAA).2Py shows only one broad band (Table 3) at 13.00 kK and 14.00 kK respectively. The complex being formally of D_{4h} symmetry excludes a square planar form because a square planar copper(II) shows two bands of nearly equal intensity at about 15.00 kK corresponding to the transitions ${}^{20-22} {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ respectively. Therefore, the observed bands are identified as d-d band ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ of octahedral Cu(II) ion.

Infrared Spectra : The infrared spectra of the ligand and its complexes were recorded in the region 4000-200 cm^{-1} . The important bands and their tentative assignments (Table 4) were obtained with reference to the spectra of other carboxylate complexes as well as those of thio and amino acid complexes²³⁻²⁶. The (C-S) stretching band at 730 cm^{-1} of the ligand on complexation was found to shift to lower frequency indicating the coordination through sulphur similar to analogous systems of thiopolycarboxylic metal chelates^{1,2,24}. The metal sulphur stretching bands of the first transition metals have been reported to occur over a wide range of wave number¹⁴. The bands of monothio or dithio diketones occur at about 350 cm^{-1} but in case of thiourea adducts²⁷ bands range from 205-298 cm^{-1} . It is, therefore, quite reasonable to assume that the observed bands in the region 245-265 cm^{-1} , in these complexes, are due to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ vibrations. The symmetric COO^- stretching band in the ligand also shifted to lower frequency. The antisymmetric (COO) stretching band on complexation also shifted to lower frequencies in the region 1580-1590 cm^{-1} except in Cu(II) complex and $\Delta(\text{COO})$ was always less than 220 cm^{-1} indicates that both carboxyl groups act as bidentate. The bridging carboxylic groups of metal carboxylate complexes also show an absorption in this region. Further, the OH deformation band at 810 cm^{-1} in the ligand disappears on complexation as the ionization of the carboxylic group is envisaged in coordination. It is, therefore, concluded that coordination takes place through both sulphur and carboxylate groups. The observed strong band at 3340 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of water molecule in Cu(II) complex and the second observed

TABLE 4—TENTATIVE ASSIGNMENTS OF IMPORTANT INFRARED BANDS OF MBTAA-H₂ AND THEIR PYRIDINE COMPLEXES

(L-H ₂)	Co(L)	Ni(L)	Cu(L)2H ₂ O	Co(L) ₂ 2Py	Ni(L) ₂ 2Py	Cu(L) ₂ 2Py	Tentative Assignments
1710(s)	1590(s)	1590(s)	1650(s)	1710(s)	1710(s)	1710(s)	(COO) asym
1410(s)	1400(s)	1400(s)	1405(m)	1400(s)	1405(m)	1410(s)	(COO) sym
300	190	190(s)	245	240	250	245	(COO)
810(m)	—	—	—	—	—	—	-OH deformation
795(s)	790(s)	790(m)	785(m)	790(m)	785(m)	790(m)	(O-C=O)
730(s)	710(m)	710(m)	710(s)	705(m)	705(m)	710(s)	(C-S)
—	—	—	—	510(m)	550(m)	520(m)	(M-N)
—	250(s)	260(m)	260(m)	245(s)	265(m)	250(s)	(M-S)

L-H₂ = MBTAA-H₂ (C₈H₈S₂O₄), s=strong, m=medium.

band at 940 cm⁻¹ was, however, assigned to coordinated water molecules which was further supported by thermogravimetric analysis indicating the loss of one molecule of water at 145° (weight loss=6.00%, theoretical=6.130%) and another at 160° (weight loss=13.00%, theoretical=12.30%). Thus Cu(II) complex is six coordinated and the two coordination positions are occupied by two water molecules. On the other hand, in case of, anhydrous Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes, the magnetic and spectral data indicate that these complexes are octahedral.

Pyridine Complexes: The magnetic moment and electronic spectra of these complexes indicate that the central metal ion is six coordinated, with high-spin essentially octahedral configuration. For this two most likely possibilities are: (a) Coordination via two N- and two S-atoms and two O-atoms of the (COO) groups, or (b) Coordination via two -N atoms and four O-atoms of (COO) groups. A comparison of (MBTAA-H₂) and their complexes with pyridine (Table 4) helps to distinguish between these two possibilities.

The (C-S) stretching band on complexation was found to shift to lower frequency indicating the coordination through sulphur. This was further supported by metal sulphur band observed in the region of 225-260 cm⁻¹. The position of the bands of antisymmetric stretching vibrations of the carboxylic groups as well as the difference of the antisymmetric and symmetric vibrations, Δ(COO) always higher than 220 cm⁻¹ indicate the covalent character of the carboxyl-metal bond^{28,29} indicate that MBTAA reacts as a tetradentate. The coordination of carboxylic oxygen was further supported by the disappearance of -OH deformation band at 810 cm⁻¹ in free ligand. The ligand MBTAA-H₂ as well as its Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes have no absorption band in the region 400-600 cm⁻¹ whereas the (M-N) stretching band in the chelated Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes usually appears in the region 400-600 cm⁻¹^{30,31}. Thus the observed bands in the region 510-550 cm⁻¹ in all pyridine complexes are due to (M-N) stretching vibrations which lie in plain and out of plain deformation coordination of pyridine to the metal ion.

The above facts suggest that pyridine complexes are octahedral and their coordination sphere is completed via two N- and two S- atoms and two O-atoms of (COO) groups.

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